

ETIOLOGY AND DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES OF CHRONIC COUGH SYNDROME IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Chronic cough syndrome is one of the most common and complex diagnostic problems in pediatric practice. In clinical practice, cough lasting more than 4 weeks in children is considered chronic cough. This condition leads to a decrease in the child's quality of life, sleep and eating disorders, and increased anxiety in parents. In most cases, chronic cough is not an independent disease, but a clinical sign of pathology of the respiratory system or other systems. The anatomical and physiological characteristics of the children's body, immaturity of the immune system, and hypersensitivity to external environmental factors play an important role in the development of chronic cough. In practice, chronic cough is often incorrectly assessed and ineffective antibacterial treatment is prescribed for a long time. Therefore, it is important to identify the etiological factors of chronic cough syndrome and develop the right diagnostic approaches.

Introduction

Chronic cough syndrome is one of the most common and complex diagnostic problems in pediatric practice. In clinical practice, cough lasting more than 4 weeks in children is considered chronic cough. This condition leads to a decrease in the child's quality of life, sleep and eating disorders, and increased anxiety in parents. In most cases, chronic cough is not an independent disease, but a clinical sign of pathology of the respiratory system or other systems. The anatomical and physiological characteristics of the children's body, immaturity of the immune system, and hypersensitivity to external environmental factors play an important role in the development of chronic cough. In practice, chronic cough is often incorrectly assessed and ineffective antibacterial treatment is prescribed for a long time. Therefore, it is important to identify the etiological factors of chronic cough syndrome and develop the right diagnostic approaches.

Research objective

To identify the main etiological factors of chronic cough syndrome in children and evaluate the effectiveness of modern diagnostic approaches.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on the example of children diagnosed with chronic cough syndrome who were under observation in the pediatric and pulmonology departments. The study was carried out retrospectively and partially prospectively. The age, gender, duration

and nature of cough (dry or wet), time of exacerbation during the day, and association with physical exertion were assessed. When collecting anamnesis, allergic predisposition, family history, frequent respiratory infections, passive smoking, and living conditions were taken into account. Along with clinical examinations, a complete blood count, eosinophil count, inflammatory markers, chest X-ray, and, if necessary, spirometry and ENT examination were performed. The results obtained were analyzed by dividing into groups according to etiological factors.

Results and discussion

According to the results of the analysis, it was determined that the etiological structure of chronic cough syndrome in children is multifactorial. The most common causes were upper respiratory tract pathologies (adenoiditis, chronic rhinitis and sinusitis), recurrent and chronic bronchitis, bronchial asthma and allergic diseases. In a significant part of the children involved in the study, chronic cough was worse at night and in the morning, which was associated with postnasal drip and bronchial hyperreactivity. In children with an allergic background, dry, prolonged cough prevailed, and laboratory tests revealed eosinophilia and an allergic history. In cases associated with bronchial asthma, cough was noted to worsen after physical exertion or contact with allergens. In some children, chronic cough was associated with gastroesophageal reflux, and the cough was characterized by worsening after eating and in the supine position. Analysis of diagnostic approaches showed that in chronic cough syndrome, it is not enough to be limited to clinical symptoms alone. A comprehensive assessment of clinical, laboratory and instrumental examinations significantly increases the possibility of identifying the etiological factor. In particular, spirometry and allergy tests are important in the early detection of bronchial asthma.

Conclusion

Chronic cough syndrome in children has a multifactorial etiology and develops in connection with pathologies of the respiratory system and other systems. The most common etiological factors are upper respiratory tract diseases, bronchial asthma, and allergic conditions. In the diagnosis of chronic cough, it is important to evaluate clinical signs in conjunction with laboratory and instrumental examinations. Correct and early diagnosis helps to reduce ineffective treatment and improve the quality of life in children.

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